

AIRBORNE LASER COMMUNICATIONS SCINTILLATION MEASUREMENTS

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ABSTRACT

As part of the HAVE LACE (Laser Airborne Communications Experiment) program, optical scintillation data was collected and is being analyzed. This data will be used to examine the effects of scintillation on air-to-air laser communication performance. The HAVE LACE terminals use direct detection of a pulsed diode laser. The random variations in received signal strength, called scintillation, are caused by the time varying index of refraction, called atmospheric turbulence. The scintillation data that was collected is compared to terrestrial scintillation data in an effort to validate atmospheric turbulence models. Valid models can then be used to aid in the design of air-to-air laser communication terminals that provide acceptable probability of error performance.

INTRODUCTION

Successful design of an atmospheric laser communications terminal requires an understanding of atmospheric turbulence induced scintillation of the optical signal. Laser beam scintillation is small scale interference within the beam cross section due to turbulence induced fluctuations of the refractive index of the atmosphere, causing variations in the spatial power density at the receiver. The variations in the spatial power density at the receiver manifest themselves as fades and surges of the detected optical signal. By understanding the statistics and power spectrum of the fades and surges communications terminals can be designed to achieve needed levels of performance by employing optimized choices of increased link margin and error coding.

Extensive research has been done to characterize and model the effects of atmospheric turbulence on terrestrial laser communications links. However, limited work has been accomplished in collecting data for validating atmospheric scintillation models associated with airborne laser communications links.

As part of the HAVE LACE (Laser Airborne Communications Experiment) program optical scintillation data was collected and is being analyzed. The analysis will aid in the determination of the degree of scintillation to be expected from the air-to-air communications channel and the effects of scintillation on communications performance. The HAVE LACE

terminals use direct detection of pulsed laser energy, therefore, the random variations in the received signal strength, can be used to evaluate the atmospheric turbulence induced scintillation. The collected data is being reduced and compared with a theoretical analysis of air-to-air communications links. The objective of the analysis is to identify deviations in the collected data from predictions based on current theory and to explain the results in terms of communications performance.

HAVE LACE OVERVIEW

The Satellite Communications Group of the Air Force Wright Aeronautical Laboratories (AFWAL) at Wright-Patterson AFB, Ohio managed the HAVE LACE program and conducted the flight tests. In an effort to demonstrate the feasibility of air-to-air laser communications AFWAL began the HAVE LACE program in 1983 under the sponsorship of the Headquarters Air Force Systems Command, New Concept and Initiatives Office. The technology for laser communications using small semiconductor laser diodes has been available for some time. Optical acquisition and tracking systems have been developed in the past for a wide variety of applications. Early in 1984, the Air Force established a contract with GTE Government Systems of Mountain View, California, to develop two airborne laser communications terminals and furnish these terminals to the Air Force for a flight test program. These terminals were not advanced development models but feasibility models using basically "off-the-shelf" technology to quickly provide the Air Force with equipment for the HAVE LACE demonstration and test program.

In order to demonstrate the feasibility of laser communications, flight tests were performed to analyze acquisition, tracking, communications, and scintillation, at operationally significant ranges. The HAVE LACE program was divided into three major areas: design and development of the laser terminals, modification of the testbed aircraft and installation of the terminals, and system test including both ground and flight testing. The two HAVE LACE terminals, furnished by GTE for use during the program, consisted of a laser transceiver and an acquisition/tracking system. GTE supported the aircraft modifications and terminal installation in two Air Force C-135 aircraft operated and maintained by the 4950th Test Wing. AFWAL conducted the flight test of the terminals and evaluated their performance.

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The terminals consisted of a laser transmitter powered by a 100 watt peak-power diode array operating at the infrared wavelength of 904 nanometers, a quadrature receiver using four avalanche photodiodes, a gimballed optical head with 11.3 cm diameter optics, and associated controls. This equipment was installed in an equipment rack with the optical head mounted in a two-axis gimbal at the rear of the rack. The entire system was placed next to a side window in each of the aircraft.

System operation began with initialization of the acquisition process. Each operator provided inputs to their terminal designating the most probable location for the cooperating aircraft based on visual sighting, known flight paths, or other navigation inputs. These inputs defined the center point for a 10 degree by 4 degree uncertainty region. Both terminals started in the responder mode where the terminals slowly scanned its uncertainty region. When an operator wanted to initiate the link, he switched his terminal to the initiating mode and it rapidly scanned its uncertainty region until the two fields of view were mutually aligned. The initiator's fast scan covered the entire scan pattern in less time than it takes for the field of view of the slow scan of the responder to pass across a point. Mutual alignment was thus assured, to within the error allowed by the fields of view, within one scan of the responder. When the terminals were mutually aligned, an optical signal was detected by each terminal and a small scan pattern used to refine alignment. After accurate tracking was established, timing synchronization began and either communications could be evaluated or scintillation data collected.

To accurately measure the scintillation, a special mode of operation was added to the terminals. In this mode of operation one terminal sends a steady stream of 80 nsec pulses at 10 Kpps and the other terminal continuously receives these pulses and detects the peak level of each pulse. Tracking at the transmitting terminal during these measurements is accomplished using only gyro stabilization, however, measurements are limited to 30 seconds so the tracking drift is minimized. The sampling of the scintillation provides information about fades and surges with frequencies up to about 5 KHz. The scintillation spectra is not expected to contain any components greater than this. A demodulator using a peak level detector followed by a sample and hold allowed the peak levels of the short pulses to be recorded on standard recording equipment. The output of the scintillation demodulator simply tracks the fluctuations, thus requiring a recording bandwidth of only 5 KHz. Flight profiles for these tests were carefully controlled so that misalignment of the two systems did not induce fluctuations. Parallel paths were maintained at constant altitude during all scintillation tests.

The HAVE LACE test program consisted of 16 flights from which 55 hours of test data was collected. Scintillation data was collected on 6

of the test flights. Most of the scintillation data was taken at altitudes around 30,000 feet and aircraft separations of 25 nautical miles. Air speeds during the scintillation runs usually varied between 350 to 400 knots.

SCINTILLATION

Literature on the subject of line-of-sight optical propagation through turbulence is extensive. However, the most important and influential theoretical development of the subject is that of V. I. Tatarski [1,2] and L. A. Chernoff [3]. The combination of their work has been the foundation for most of the work that has followed. A collection of review articles on the subject are available [4] and provide a concise development of turbulence theory.

Even with the extensive interest shown toward the theoretical development of this subject, predictions of the effects of atmospheric turbulence on optical propagation can be checked only by in situ measurements. The atmosphere is inhomogeneous and statistically nonstationary which precludes the use of simple models in characterizing it as a communications channel. Of interest to optical propagation research is the variation of refractive index resulting from variation of the density of the air. The air density depends on temperature and pressure. However, pressure fluctuations are rapidly dissipated and have negligible effects when compared to that of the longer lasting temperature variations.

Sunlight incident on the earth's surface is absorbed and, in turn, as the earth re-emits this energy the surface air layer is heated. As the warmed surface layer air becomes less dense it rises, mixing turbulently with cooler air. Therefore, the air temperature varies randomly from point to point in the atmosphere (on the order of 0.1 - 1°C) and is a function of altitude and wind speed due to the turbulent mixing. These turbulent eddies result in an ever changing index of refraction of the air, with variations which are typically on the order of 10^{-6} [4]. While the refractive index variation is very small, in situations of practical interest a laser beam propagates through a large number of these inhomogeneities. This initially produces optical phase effects (leading to angle of arrival fluctuations or beam wander), intensity fluctuations (scintillation), and beam broadening. It is the intensity fluctuations of the communications signal which are of interest here. The effect of atmospheric turbulence depends on the scale size of the turbulent eddies which range from a millimeter to several hundred meters or larger [5]. Scintillations of the communications signal are caused primarily by irregularities having the size of a Fresnel zone, $(\lambda L)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, for a wavelength, λ and path length L . Therefore, at optical frequencies and path lengths of a few kilometers scintillation is caused by scale sizes of only a few centimeters. The time required for light to propagate through these

turbulent eddies is only a fraction of their "fluctuation time." Therefore, the time dependence of the refractive index changes is often suppressed and attention focused on spatial properties [6].

In communications the temporal properties of the turbulence are of interest and Taylor's "frozen turbulence" hypothesis is invoked. This hypothesis assumes that a given realization of the random refractive index is "frozen" and drifts across the receiver aperture with constant velocity determined by the local wind conditions. While the communications signal experiences fades and surges due to scintillation it is the signal fades which most limits the communications performance. Therefore, the frequency spectra (duration and recurrence) and the depth (probability a fade will exceed a threshold) of fades are important to characterize. Understanding the fading characteristics allows the design engineer to achieve a level of performance based on probability of error (P_F) by adding signal margin and employing coding techniques for the turbulent atmospheric optical channel. V.W.S. Chan [7] and R. Gagliardi and S. Karp [8] have discussed coding techniques appropriate for this channel. Knowing the expected depth of fading gives the designer the option of employing the brute force technique of adding signal margin in either exceedance or expectation approaches as presented by R. Gagliardi and S. Karp [9]. As more knowledge is gained about the statistical nature of the optical communications channel optimum combinations of coding and link margin can be used to achieve required communications performance levels. In particular, the long high altitude horizontal path atmospheric channel is least characterized. Results provided by G. J. Morris [10] involving horizontal high altitude airborne scintillation measurements over short paths and the opportunity to take part in the HAVE LACE program led to the motivation to perform the current work.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The frequency spectra of scintillations is related to both the size of the turbulent eddies and the rate at which they move across the receiver aperture. Much data has been analyzed for terrestrial scintillation and the frequencies have been found to range from 0.1 to 100 Hz [11]. Scintillation at ground level results from large turbulent eddies whose rate of motion is due to wind speeds, thus low frequencies fluctuations are expected. At altitude the turbulent eddies are much smaller and their rate of movement is, by the "frozen turbulence" assumption, the result of aircraft airspeed.

Tatarski [1] presented the first discussion of the temporal power spectral density. Equation (1) provides an expression for the reciprocal of the time required for a Fresnel-zone size disturbance to move across the line-of-sight,

$$f_0 = \frac{V}{(2\pi \lambda L)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (1)$$

where V is the perpendicular airspeed, L is the path length and f_0 is related to the corner frequency of the spectrum, f_c , by [4]

$$\frac{f_c}{f_0} = 1.43 \quad (2)$$

For the HAVE LACE flights (1) and (2) yield corner frequencies between 475 and 600 Hz for airspeeds of 300 to 350 knots. A representative frequency spectrum from our test flights shows f_c to be approximately 100 Hz (Figure 1). This frequency spectrum was obtained by Fast Fourier Transforming (FFT) 0.4 seconds of scintillation data and then taking the ensemble average of 74 such FFT's. The magnitude of the ensemble average is used to represent the power spectral density.

Using the flight parameters given in Figure 1 the theoretical corner frequencies as given by (1) and (2) is 502 Hz. The factor of 5 difference in the observed corner frequency is possibly due to aperture averaging. The phenomena of aperture averaging and receiver high frequency filtering can be observed in the curves of Figure 2. Assuming a circular receiver aperture Tatarski [1] has obtained the detailed shape of the irradiance power spectrum for propagation along a horizontal path (Figure 2). The curve for $\rho = 0$ in Figure 2 represents the spectrum of the signal irradiance for a point receiver, where ρ is related to the radius of the aperture, R , by $\rho = R(2\pi/\lambda L)^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

Ishimaru [4] has obtained the asymptotic form of the spectra for the case $\rho = 0$ and found that the spectrum tends to decrease as $f^{-8/3}$. The spectrum of Figure 1 decreases as f^{-2} which is consistent with the flattening of the curves of Figure 2 as ρ increases. This f^{-2} behavior of the analyzed data adds support to the aperture averaging assumption. Exact relationships between f_0 , f_c , and ρ for aperture averaging and the HAVE LACE data have not been established. Efforts continue to find these relationships and resolve the discrepancies between the data and the theoretical form of the temporal power spectral density.

The depth of fading due to scintillation can be directly related to the probability that fades of a certain depth will occur. Tatarski's [1] and all subsequent treatments of this subject predict that the probability distribution of the logarithm of the intensity is a normal distribution. Ground scintillation data is in good agreement with this prediction and our initial flight test results show agreement with a log normal distribution (Figure 3).

CONCLUSION

The HAVE LACE program provided a unique opportunity to perform high altitude scintillation measurements over extended path lengths. While airborne testing is by its dynamic nature very challenging and difficult to perform, in situ measurements are necessary if practical application of laser communications theory is to be accomplished. Though the results presented here are preliminary, we are encouraged by the reasonably good agreement with theory. Further, data reduction and analysis is in progress and these results will be presented at future conferences.

REFERENCES

1. V.I. Tatarski, Wave Propagation in a Turbulent Medium, McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York, 1961.
2. V.I. Tatarski, The Effects of the Turbulent Atmosphere on Wave Propagation, National Science Foundation Report TT-68-50464, 1968.
3. L.A. Chernoff, Wave Propagation in a Random Medium, Mc-Graw-Hill Book Company, New York, 1960.
4. J.W. Strohbehn, editor, Laser Beam Propagation in the Atmosphere, Springer-Verlag, New York, 1978.
5. R.S. Lawrence, G.R. Ochs, and S.F. Clifford, "Measurements of Atmospheric Turbulence Relevant to Optical Propagation," Journal of the Optical Society of America, Vol. 60, No. 6, pp 826-830, June 1970.
6. J.W. Goodman, Statistical Optics, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1985.
7. V.W.S. Chan, "Coding for the Turbulent Atmospheric Optical Channel," IEEE Transactions on Comm, Vol. COM-30, No. 1, pp 269-275, January 1982.
8. R. Gagliardi and S. Karp, "M-ary Poisson Detection and Optical Communications," IEEE Transactions on Comm Technology, Vol. COM-17, No. 2, pp 208-216, April 1969.
9. R. Gagliardi and S. Karp, Optical Communications, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1976.
10. G.J. Morris, "Airborne laser beam scintillation measurements at high altitudes," Journal of the Optical Society of America, Vol. 63, No. 3, pp 263-270, March 1973.
11. R.S. Lawrence and J.W. Strohbehn, "A survey of clear-air propagation effects relevant to optical communications," Proc IEEE, Vo. 58, pp 1523-1545, October 1970.

FIGURE 1

Representative Power Spectral Density

FIGURE 2

Theoretical Form of the Irradiance Power Spectrum.

FIGURE 3

Received Power Probability Distribution with Normal Probability Density for Comparison.